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tate in dioxane-water (Table 2), while the oxidation rate, being very slow, is not measurable in acetic acid-water. This indicates that acetic acid is not a good solvent in the selenium dioxide oxidation of diphenylmethane. However, acetic acid has been found to be a good solvent in the selenium dioxide oxidation of olefins⁶⁻¹³, ketones^{1-4,9}, ester¹⁴, etc.

Unlike chromic acid⁵ oxidation of diphenylmethane in glacial acetic acid, the acid catalysed oxidation of diphenylmethane by selenium dioxide in dioxane-water, under the condition $[\text{SeO}_2] \ll [\text{diphenylmethane}]$, proceeds smoothly till the oxidant is consumed completely (Table 2).

TABLE 2—ACID CATALYSED OXIDATION OF DIPHENYLMETHANE BY SELENIUM DIOXIDE UNDER CONDITION $[\text{SeO}_2] \ll [\text{DPM}]$ IN 80%(v/v) DIOXANE-WATER

Time min.	0	30	60	90	120	150
$[\text{SeO}_2]$ in ml of	4.1	3.5	3.0	2.6	2.2	1.8
$\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$	1.4	1.1	0.9	0.75	0.6	0.5
$10^3 k \text{ min}^{-1}$	—	2.29	2.26	2.22	2.25	2.38
($k = k_1/2.303$)	2.59	2.75	2.74	2.75	2.78	2.76

The temperature coefficient for the present reaction is nearly 2, while relatively small effect of temperature was observed⁵ in the chromic acid oxidation of diphenylmethane.

The present kinetic investigation gives information on the mechanism of acid catalysed oxidation of diphenylmethane by selenium dioxide, which has not been reported previously.

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Studies on Resorcinol Formaldehyde Cationic Resins†

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SYNTHESIS and study of ion exchangers is of interest because of their large scale use particularly in analytical chemistry and in the softening of water. There is a greater need now either to find out altogether newer resins which are economical compared to the existing exchangers or to identify substitutes which can partly replace the polymeric content of the existing exchangers to a considerable extent while retaining the properties of the parent resins.

Earlier work done has revealed that coke¹, sawdust², lignite could be substituted upto 30-40 percent in phenolic cationities. Such a substitution did not have any adverse effect and in addition the composites obtained were macroporous.

In fact, cation exchangers can be made from almost any material which reacts with sulphuric acid without being dissolved, such as the sulphonated olive pits³, and nut shells and spent coffee⁴, tar⁵, paper⁶, cotton, etc.

The present work is an attempt to prepare and study the properties of sulphonated resorcinol formaldehyde cation exchangers substituted partially by sulphonated charcoal obtained from coconut fibre.

Experimental

Preparation of the sample: Reagents used were resorcinol and formaldehyde (B.D.H.), and concentrated H_2SO_4 (sp.gr.1.82). Coconut fibre was procured from local industries and cleaned before use.

Resorcinol (10 g) and conc. H_2SO_4 (12.5 ml) were mixed slowly with constant cooling. Then the

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mixture was heated on a water bath for 1 h and polymerised with 37% formaldehyde (12.5 ml). The content were heated for 6 h and the resinous mass was washed free of acid and cured at 70° for several hours.

Sample II was prepared by adding conc. H₂SO₄ to coconut fibre and heated on a water bath for 6 h and then washed it free from acid and dried at 70° overnight. The coconut fibre was thus carbonized and sulphonated. Similarly, samples with 20, 25, 30, 40, 60 and 80% coconut charcoal were prepared by adding 6.5, 8.7, 11.1, 17.3, 26 and 39 g of coconut charcoal to sulphonated resorcinol and polymerised using formaldehyde.

Physical measurements :

(a) *Density :* The density of the resin in both the hydrated and dehydrated states was obtained with the aid of a specific gravity bottle, in water and in toluene, respectively.

(b) *Particle size :* Particle size was determined by sieving the samples through 200 mesh.

TABLE 1—AMOUNTS OF REAGENTS USED AND YIELDS OF COMPOSITES

Sample	Weight of reagent taken, g		Amount of coconut charcoal added g	Yield g	Coconut charcoal in resin %
	Resorcinol	Formaldehyde			
A	10	12.5	0	26	0
B	10	12.5	6.5	30.8	20
C	10	12.5	8.7	34.0	25
D	10	12.5	11.1	36.4	30
E	10	12.5	17.3	42.1	40
F	10	12.5	26.0	51.1	60
G	10	12.5	39.0	62.9	80

(c) *Attrition effect :* Attrition effect on the samples were compared with that of the unsubstituted resin as follows. Both types of the samples were initially sieved to give batches containing particles greater than 200 mesh size. They were swollen in water and shaken continuously for 6 h. Samples were separated by filtration, dried and weighed. Subsequently these were sieved on a 200 mesh and the amounts of substance passing through the holes were weighed.

(d) *Swelling :* Percentage swelling measurements were made by allowing the samples to equilibrate in water overnight. The wet sample weight was taken as M_w and the corresponding dry weight M_d was obtained after drying the sample at 70°. The gravimetric percent (α) swelling was calculated as

$$\alpha = \frac{M_w - M_d}{M_d} \times 100.$$

(e) *Identification of inorganic groups :* The infrared spectra (KBr) of the samples were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer apparatus.

(f) *Exchange capacity :* Exchange capacity measurements were made by the method followed by Kunin⁷. The samples were converted into the H⁺- form by washing with HCl followed by distilled water to remove acidity. Known weight of the samples in the H⁺- forms were equilibrated with standard solution (0.01M) of Na, Ca⁺⁺, Mg⁺⁺ and Zn⁺⁺ ions.

Test columns were prepared from graduated burettes with cotton-wool plugs and known weight of the sample. The sample was made into a slurry with distilled water. The burette column fitted with cotton-wool was filled with the slurry. Sodium sulphate solution (25 ml, 0.01M) was added slowly to the column in 2 or 3 portions. The eluted solution was collected. The H⁺ liberated in the solution was titrated against standard NaOH solution (0.01M) with phenolphthalein as indicator.

The ion exchange resin was regenerated by washing it with HCl (25 ml, 4M) and subsequently with water. The filtrate was tested for the excess of chloride ion with silver nitrate. The resin was now filled with 25 ml portions of Ca⁺⁺/Mg⁺⁺/Zn⁺⁺ solutions of known strength at the rate of 2-3 ml min⁻¹. Solutions were prepared from calcium chloride, magnesium sulphate and zinc sulphate (all AnalaR) salts. The filtrate was collected and the amount of the ions exchanged were determined by titrating against standard EDTA. By this EDTA titration, the decrease in Ca⁺⁺/Mg⁺⁺/Zn⁺⁺ ion concentration in the supernatant was measured and the exchange capacity of the composites were calculated (Table 4).

Results and Discussion

The percentage composition and physical characteristics of the different exchangers are given in Table 1. The average swelling percentage and the densities are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—PERCENTAGE SWELLING AND ABSOLUTE DENSITIES

Sample	Coconut charcoal in resin %	Average swelling %	Absolute density	
			In hydrated state g ml ⁻¹	In dehydrated state g ml ⁻¹
A	0	122.90	2.298	1.599
B	20	89.45	1.472	1.643
C	25	92.60	1.352	1.627
D	30	90.36	1.393	1.580
E	40	97.68	1.318	1.612
F	60	112.80	1.401	1.490
G	80	120.30	1.395	1.499
H	100	128.80	1.374	1.482

The average percent swelling decreases from 100 percent resin to pure carbon. It is not necessary for a resin to swell in a solvent in order to exhibit appreciable ion exchange capacity. The results in column 3 of Table 2 show that the swelling of the pure resin is greater than other samples except pure

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charcoal. From this it can be stated that the porosity and polarity are greater in the pure resin. But the swelling in the sample with 80 percent charcoal is higher than the samples with the less percentage of charcoal. This may be due to high porous nature of charcoal. Volumetric swelling is not high, because there are macroreticular and nongel pores.

The absolute densities both in the hydrated and dehydrated states are not much different between the pure resin and the composites. It shows high porous nature for the pure resin and the composites.

TABLE 3—ATTRITION EFFECT ON EXCHANGERS

Sample	Coconut charcoal in resin %	Weight of resin taken before shaking g	After shaking	
			Amount passed through 200 mesh g	%
A	0	1.8490	0.3684	19.93
B	20	1.6590	0.2416	14.56
C	25	1.6018	0.2324	14.5
D	30	1.5800	0.2142	13.80
E	40	1.5274	0.2970	19.45
F	60	1.7280	0.2648	15.32
G	80	1.9100	0.2552	13.35
H	100	1.9732	0.2460	12.45

As seen from column 3 of Table 3, the samples before shaking are basically made up of particles above 200 mesh in size. After shaking for several hours and repeating the sieving process it is observed that the percentage of particles less than 200 mesh in size formed due to attritional braking during sieving is not appreciable. This is the same for pure resin and the composites B to G. Thus, much difference is not seen in the attritional stability between the pure and the composites, although in the

latter it is possible that the resin might have formed in the capillaries of charcoal particles.

The apparent capacity for the exchange of Na^+ (0.01M) and $\text{Ca}^{++}/\text{Mg}^{++}/\text{Zn}^{++}$ (0.01M) on the H^+ -form of the exchangers are listed in Table 4.

TABLE 4—CAPACITY OF H^+ -FORM OF COMPOSITES

Sample	Coconut charcoal in resin %	Exchange column capacity estimated meq g ⁻¹			
		Na 0.01M	Ca 0.01M EDTA	Mg 0.01M EDTA	Zn 0.01M EDTA
A	0	0.810	1.650	1.51	1.430
B	20	0.770	1.40	1.47	1.410
C	25	0.750	0.805	1.00	1.250
D	30	0.758	1.200	1.46	1.40
E	40	0.605	1.08	1.14	1.06
F	60	0.480	1.062	1.20	1.06
G	80	0.360	1.880	0.80	0.840
H	100	0.192	0.730	0.702	0.803

As expected the exchange capacities are higher for bivalent ions as compared to Na^+ at the same concentration. Fig. 1 shows the plot of column exchange capacity vs coconut fibre charcoal content in the resin for Na, Ca^{++} , Mg^{++} , and Zn^{++} ions. It is seen that though there is a continuous decrease in the capacity of coconut charcoal the fall is not much upto 30%. This indicates that substitution of coconut fibre charcoal upto 30% is economical.

The rigidity of the matrix is proved from swelling measurements. So, these resins may be useful where they are required to stand large osmotic shock. The inherent porosity of these resins are proved by density measurements. Since they have inherent porosity the resins may be useful

Fig. 1. Exchange capacity vs percentage of coconut fibre charcoal in the resin.

in nonaqueous solvents. As a result of porosity these resins may be used for the exchange of big ions of the type $(NR_4)^{4+}$ and hence, in pharmaceutical industry.

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Synthesis of Aryl Thioureas and Related Compounds as Potential Fungicides

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THE pesticidal activity of substituted thioureas is due to the presence of N—C=S group. Various 4-thiazolidones are shown to possess pesticidal¹, miticidal², antimicrobial^{3,4}, antibacterial⁵, antitubercular⁶, amaebicidal⁷, and fungicidal⁸⁻¹⁰ activities. 3-Aryl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinones have also been reported for their fungicidal activity¹¹. Keeping this in view some aryl thioureas, 4-thiazolidones and related compounds were prepared.

Methylantranilate was condensed with aryl isothiocyanate to yield *N*-*o*-carbomethoxyphenyl-*N'*-aryl thioureas (I). I on heating with chloroacetic acid and fused sodium acetate gave the corresponding 3-*o*-carbomethoxyphenyl-2-aryliminothiazolid-4-ones (II), which with anhydrous sodium acetate and an aldehyde produced 5-arylideno-3-*o*-carbomethoxyphenyl-2-aryliminothiazolid-4-ones (III). III on bromination yielded the corresponding dibromides (IV).

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected and purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. Structure

assigned to II was confirmed by hydrolysis. The structure of the compounds was confirmed by elemental analysis, ir and nmr spectra. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 190 spectrophotometer and nmr on Varian EM 360 spectrophotometer at 60 MHz.

***N*-*o*-Carbomethoxyphenyl-*N'*-arylthioureas (I):** A methanolic solution of methyl anthranilate (0.01 M) and arylisothiocyanate (0.01 M) was refluxed for 3 h and cooled. The product separating out was filtered, washed and crystallised from aqueous ethanol. The compounds thus prepared are listed in Table 1.

3-*o*-Carbomethoxyphenyl-2-aryliminothiazolid-4-ones (II): A methanolic solution of thiourea (I) (0.01 M), chloroacetic acid (0.01 M) and fused sodium acetate (2.0 g) was refluxed for 5 h, cooled and poured into water. The solid separating out was filtered, washed with water and crystallised with aqueous ethanol. The compounds thus prepared are given in Table 2.

Structural confirmation of II: A methanolic solution (10 ml) of the above 4-thiazolidone (1.0 g) and conc. HCl (2 ml) was refluxed for 3 to 4 h. Methanol was distilled off and the residue poured into water. The precipitate obtained was washed with water and crystallised. Each one of the compounds (II) was hydrolysed and the resulting compound 3-(*o*-carbomethoxyphenyl)thiazolidine-2,4-dione, had the same m.p. 240°. M.m.p. remained the same. It could not, however, be synthesised.

5-Arylideno-3-*o*-carbomethoxyphenyl-2-aryliminothiazolid-4-ones (III): A mixture of 3-*o*-carbomethoxyphenyl-2-aryliminothiazolid-4-one (0.01 M),